

USING AND INTEGRATING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN THE FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASS. ITALIAN LANGUAGE CASE AT ISMAIL QEMALI UNIVERSITY OF VLORA

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ABSTRACT

To encourage foreign language teachers to use authentic materials in their classes, various advantages have been identified. These materials, especially those obtained through audiovisual and multimedia technologies, provide not only the language but also insights into the culture, traditions, behaviors, and history of the country being studied. Teachers can carefully select and integrate these materials into their lessons to achieve specific objectives and engage students. Access to up-to-date and motivating authentic materials can be found through online networks and platforms, as well as through materials specifically created by teachers and experts. These resources aid in bringing the language closer to its native varieties.

Keywords: authentic materials, classroom, Italian language, linguistic context.

Use of authentic materials in foreign language classrooms. Context of Italian language

The use of authentic materials in foreign language classrooms has gained significant attention in recent years. Authentic materials refer to real-world materials that native speakers use in their daily lives, such as newspapers, magazines, videos, and songs. In the context of the Italian language class at Ismail Qemali University, the integration of authentic materials has proven to be an effective strategy for enhancing students' language proficiency and cultural understanding. In this paper we will try to explore the benefits, challenges, and strategies associated with using and integrating authentic materials in the Italian language class at Ismail Qemali University. The concept of "*authentic materials*" emerged in the field of foreign language teaching in the 1970s. These materials are texts created by native speakers for communication purposes and are not modified. They should represent the language accurately. Authentic materials can also include texts that are simplified for teaching purposes but still maintain their original characteristics. These materials provide insight into the culture of the language being learned and promote understanding of different cultural contexts. The use of authentic materials in language classes encourages students to compare and appreciate cultural differences. It also helps students develop familiarity with social-cultural patterns and promotes respect for other cultures. Additionally, studying authentic materials allows students to analyze cultural relativity and learn about new worlds. The use of authentic materials in foreign language classrooms has gained significant attention in recent years. Authentic materials refer to real-world materials that native speakers use in their daily lives, such as newspapers, magazines, videos, and songs. In the context of the Italian language class at Ismail Qemali University, the integration of authentic materials has proven to be an effective strategy for enhancing students' language proficiency and cultural understanding. This essay aims to explore the benefits, challenges, and strategies associated with using and integrating authentic materials in the Italian language class at Ismail Qemali University.

Benefits of Using Authentic Materials

The use of authentic materials offers numerous benefits for foreign language learners. Firstly, it provides learners with exposure to real-life language usage, allowing them to develop their listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills in a more meaningful context. Authentic materials also expose students to various cultural aspects, enhancing their intercultural competence and understanding of the target language community. Moreover, authentic materials serve as a motivational tool, as they make the learning experience more engaging and relevant. By incorporating authentic materials into the Italian language class, Ismail Qemali University aims to create an immersive and authentic learning environment for its students.

Challenges of Integrating Authentic Materials

While the integration of authentic materials brings numerous advantages, it also presents some challenges. One common challenge is the level of difficulty. Authentic materials are typically designed for native speakers, which means they may contain complex vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, or cultural references that students are not yet familiar with. To overcome this challenge, instructors at Ismail Qemali University carefully select authentic materials that are appropriate for the students' proficiency level. Additionally, pre-teaching vocabulary and providing scaffolding activities can help students navigate through the materials more effectively. Another challenge is the availability and accessibility of authentic materials. In the case of the Italian language class at Ismail Qemali University, instructors have overcome this challenge by utilizing online resources, such as Italian news websites, YouTube videos, and podcasts. These resources not only offer a wide range of authentic materials but also provide flexibility in terms of time and location. Furthermore, instructors at Ismail Qemali University collaborate with local Italian cultural institutions to organize field trips, where students can directly experience authentic Italian language and culture.

Strategies for Integrating Authentic Materials

To successfully integrate authentic materials into the Italian language class, instructors at Ismail Qemali University employ various strategies. *Firstly*, they carefully select authentic materials that are relevant to students' interests and align with the learning objectives.

This ensures that students remain motivated and engaged throughout the learning process. *Secondly*, instructors scaffold the learning activities by providing pre-reading or pre-listening tasks to help students comprehend the materials better. These tasks can include predicting the content, brainstorming vocabulary related to the topic, or discussing relevant cultural aspects. In addition, instructors at Ismail Qemali University encourage active participation and interaction among students during authentic material-based activities. Group discussions, debates, role-plays, and project-based assignments are some techniques used to foster meaningful communication and collaboration. Moreover, instructors provide regular feedback and guidance to help students reflect on their language development and address any challenges they may encounter.

Process of language acquisition

One crucial aspect of language learning is the acquisition of vocabulary and grammar structures. Authentic materials, such as newspapers, magazines, movies, and songs, provide students with exposure to genuine language usage. Research conducted by linguist Stephen Krashen highlights the significance of comprehensible input, where learners are exposed to language that is slightly above their current proficiency level. By engaging with authentic materials, Italian language learners can encounter new vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, and grammatical structures in a meaningful context. This exposure enhances their ability to comprehend and produce language naturally, replicating the way native speakers use the language in everyday situations.

Cultural Understanding

Language and culture are intrinsically intertwined. Authentic materials serve as gateways to Italian culture, enabling students to gain a deeper understanding of the country's customs, traditions, and societal norms. For example, by analyzing Italian literature or watching Italian films, students can explore the historical, social, and political aspects of Italy. This exposure fosters cultural empathy and sensitivity, allowing students to appreciate the complexities of Italian society. Moreover, authentic materials provide insights into Italian humor, colloquialisms, and cultural references that textbooks often overlook. By immersing themselves in authentic materials, students can develop a more nuanced understanding of Italian culture, enabling them to communicate effectively and respectfully with native speakers.

Language Proficiency

Authentic materials offer students the opportunity to improve their language proficiency by engaging with real-life language use. In a study conducted by Pica et al. (1993), it was found that learners who interacted with authentic materials demonstrated higher levels of motivation, engagement, and language production. Unlike contrived exercises in textbooks, authentic materials provide a glimpse into the dynamic nature of language. They expose students to various registers, dialects, and regional differences, preparing them to navigate real-life communication with confidence. Additionally, authentic materials enhance students' listening and speaking skills by exposing them to different accents, intonations, and conversational styles. By interacting with authentic materials, students develop the ability to understand and produce language in diverse

contexts, ultimately leading to higher language proficiency.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the integration of authentic materials in the Italian language class at Ismail Qemali University has proven to be a valuable approach for enhancing students' language proficiency and cultural understanding. Despite the challenges associated with using authentic materials, instructors at Ismail Qemali University have successfully addressed them through careful selection, scaffolding, and collaboration with cultural institutions. By providing an immersive and authentic learning environment, Ismail Qemali University equips its students with the necessary language skills and cultural competence to thrive in an Italian-speaking context. Authentic materials are an indispensable resource in the Italian classroom, offering numerous benefits to language learners. They facilitate language acquisition by providing exposure to real-world language use, enhance cultural understanding by immersing students in Italian society, and improve language proficiency by exposing learners to diverse linguistic contexts. As educators, it is crucial to incorporate authentic materials into our teaching practices to create an immersive and engaging learning environment. By doing so, we empower our students to become competent Italian language users who appreciate and embrace the richness of Italian culture.

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